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**TEACHING FOR SOCIAL CHANGE: CAN
EDUCATION BRING A SOCIAL CHANGE IN A
SOCIETY?**

Prof. Ketan V.*, Sutaria, Jay V, Gala**

*Lecturer, Bal-Bharati's MJP College of Commerce

**Student, Bal-Bharati's MJP College of Commerce

Abstract

For shaping the character of an individual education plays a very important element in life and to bring social order in the society there should be a social change. Therefore Education and Social Change goes Hand in Hand. Education preserves the values, morals and beliefs and keep factual data record which will act great utility for the future generations. It gives learner an ability to think, take rightful decisions and to innovate. It eliminates the lack of knowledge which is main stimulus for human stagnation.

Learning can initiate a social change in to order o change the viewpoint and mind-set of an individual person. Slowly there is an increase in automation in education system. This results in absorbing large volume of informational material in short time but it reduces the judgment ability of the learner because of dependability of learners on classes rather than self-learning.

It distracts the liberal thinking of learners. Society will change socially and culturally only because of education. Education act as a link for learners between socialization and expectations of society. Education is the essential technique of social progress and reform. It leads the learner towards new principles, ethics, standards, morals, ideals and help in growth of intelligence and improves the society potential for a good change.

The present paper focuses on the role of edification and technology as a mechanism of social change and growth with introduction of technology for the development of teaching-learning process. It also focuses on obligatory professional knowledge and channels the educators to develop the teaching skills so that it can be more effective. The most influential and valuable instrument of social change and social growth in current time is the education. It emphasize that education has major impact in society, but that it is allocated a conventional role because its main utility is in the socialization of the leaner and the preservation of the social order. Economically when things are going good, more support is given on education experimentation and more optimistic objectives are achieved, such as equity of educational opportunity.

Objectives

1. To understand the concept and functions of 'Social Change in Teaching'.

2. To study the perception level of learners towards change in edification socially.
3. To give brief idea about how education can transform individual with help of socialization

Methodology

The interpretations conversed in this paper are based on our conceptual understanding about the topic. We have tried to describe the topic using secondary data sources such as research paper, journal, the internet websites and related articles related to social changes in education from the newspapers, magazines and publications.

Meaning

Social change is responsive process to many types of changes, changes in the manual circumstances of life, changes in the outlook and philosophy of human being and changes that go far off human control to the biological and the corporeal personality of things.

Teaching is a procedure in which one individual edify or inculcate another individual. It is regarded as the act of communicating information to the learners in the classroom circumstances. It can also be considered as a operation of the circumstances, where the student will attain skills, knowledge and insight with his own instigation.

Introduction

Innovation in culture will only be successful with the help of culture experimentation. To bring a change in mindset of learners there is a need of socialization and that the objective could be achieved only through teachers and education.

Whenever there is discussion with teachers, they often articulate the need to be aware of the modalities of teaching subjects in better way. Teachers are always in finishing the yearly syllabus on are cleared with good marks. The image of the school and educators totally rely on examination scores of students. Some of the best educationists wonder about the importance of subjects in overall education, about its real meaning, responsibility and function of education which are prescribed by the government in their documents. The real meaning of education is to help students to make them realise their true potential.

As per policy, Role of education in India, “edification is primary for our overall development — both materialistic and spiritualistic. Education helps in purifying sensitivities and perceptions that add to national unity, construct methodical temper and self-determination of mind and spirit — thus increasing the aims of socialism, secularism and democracy. Because of education Individual power is also improved at different levels of economy adding to the country’s self-sufficiency.”

Education is not to make any arrangement for life but is it helps in imbibing the dignity, moral and values in individual life. By evaluating the relationship between education and social change, only one question arises i.e how does education lead to social change? Due to social change in education, it helps society to generate and strength and modernizes in a very

different and unique way. Education has been acknowledged as one major element of socialisation, and educators and institutions as socialising instrument.

An important role played in our life is by a teacher because of their efforts an individual become successful in career and business. An individual becomes a good human being in society and good civilian of the country with the efforts and sacrifices made by a teacher. Teachers are very well aware about the fact that students are the future potentials of any country. The efforts and sacrifices of teachers should be appreciated because they are the persons that build future nation. But it is sad to see that in today's world teachers are affected by business, politics, and society.

Social change may take place (i) When a change is needed by human, (ii) When the existing social system or network of social institutions fall short to meet the existing human needs and (iii) When human finds innovative ways for meeting their needs. A social change cannot take place in a society directly or indirectly. Only education can commence social changes by bringing modification in the viewpoint and approach of a individual. It also bring a change in pattern of social relationship and this results bringing social changes.

In order to study the connection between education and social change, it is essential to outline the contribute role of education in social change in the following manner:

1. An individual becomes a good human being in society and good civilian of the country socially with help of education
2. It establishes the principles which act as decisive factor for the examination of social change before its acceptance.
3. It originates, direct and channel social change and assists in elimination of a mass of social tribulations and melancholy.
4. It creates social change and leaders who make strenuous efforts to bring about changes in the society.
5. It assists in progression and enlargement of mind—the opportunity of knowledge for generating changes.
6. It assists in propagating knowledge and ability in the improving intelligence to work for the advancement of the society.
7. It verifies the nature of social changes which ought to bring about—slow or fast, violent or peaceful.

Suggestions

1. Promoting dynamic participation and analysis of ideas with learners.

Regrettably, professor and learners whose main objective is paper-based development often thrust for a lot of memorizing of records, information, and definitions. But this typical way of learning is not shifting the society towards right path. Educators should always try to innovate and raise lively learning opportunities, where learners can be completely affianced with the substance and engage in recreation of ideas without being castigate for going too far afield. Educators should always assist a learning environment include letting learners educate each other, setting up a method for students to ask anonymous subject question and conveying open-ended assignment in which learners are not given the intuition that they are expected to take prearranged steps in anticipation of getting “right” answer.

2. Train learners for innovative thinking instead of training them what to think.

Many studies recommend that theoretical inquisition is not above the heads of elementary-aged students. The learner impersonation and dilemma is what taken at centre stage, not a concrete idealistic mode or text. Learners are always being trained how to think instead of what to think. It is teachers responsibility to train learners for innovative learning instead of training them what to think. Teachers should try to show the difference between How to Think and What to think. Substantiation opine that learners respond well to the viewpoint in the Classroom exercise which was taught to them a week before and this resulted in improvement of students’ interpretation levels, essential judgment skills, and emotional happiness.

3. To make them judge their own capability to take optimistic steps for the advantage of society.

Teachers should always encourage learners to play an influential part in well built societal enhancement for a creation of classroom where learners are given accountability and power to make some important decision.

It is believed that if all answers are available with educators then it is assumed that learners are expected to receive If teachers have all the answers, it’s implied that students are expected to receive knowledge but cannot offer explanation or enhancement. But if educators make it clear and transparent that they also lack some sort of knowledge then learners have more opportunity to rely on their own analytical powers and problem-solving skills.

Teacher should create a learning atmosphere in which learners are taught to observe the benefit of being failure rather than learning to trepidation of doing something wrong.

4. Democratic Classroom practices establishes idea of active contribution which result in social change

Equality should be kept as “structure of illusion” in classrooms if education systems want to provide advantages of healthy democratic society. Individuals are forgotten that every day they should be participating in democracy because it’s a skill that should be practiced in our daily lives. Teachers should make classrooms more democratic than rigid, starting at a very tender age.

Learners should always be taught about the theoretical and practical aspect of learning as how to cast a vote and how that opportunity is presented to them and how their thoughts and ideas can be applied for the benefit of society.

5. Discussions among group of teachers – starting with learners educators – about the choice that can oblige social change.

If you are aware of fact or not but it is believed that Educators and school had great persuasion over society. Teachers should always encourage learners to come mutually as a group to share ideas, facts, knowledge, skill, failure and triumph. The bigger and broader these group discussion will be, teachers should come up with queries and by providing solution to queries it will help learners to know the difference between the good and bad and it will result into social change. Even if one small step is consistently, then there will be enhancement in stronger societal material, structuring better democratic methods, trying to benefit learners. As learners are survive in classroom and societies are being faked, positively a social change will be developed among learners.

It is very much crucial that teaching organization recommends empirical and objective-based guidance to sustain their individual and certified growth because learners are looking for significant careers in the social sector. Multifaceted local and universal challenges insist inventive solutions which are enlarged collaboratively by educationist with knowledge, associations, principles and ethics to successfully progress social change. There is no proper formal model for learning social change but if teachers try to bring learners to internal and external social problems then they would be able to develop effective solutions practically.

Learners will be trained to design program to provide future invention of social change leaders with a variety of proficiency—and the modesty—that they require in their work. Internal and External Experimental learning will help learners to witness innovative new approaches to social-change problems. They are would be able to examine how institutions gear up to face challenges with inspiration, compassion and a partnership-based approach, which will assist in providing a holistic set of morals, ethics, values and principles that will supply them in their future careers.

6. Creating a Desire for Change

Education not only helps in casting the outlook of learners but also assist in crafting a aspiration for change by providing right acquaintance and grind of thinking. Learners become conscious of the social tribulations and stigma like dowry, casteism, infanticide, child marriage, alcoholism, drug addiction, gambling, begging, bonded labour, child labour,

corruption, nepotism, bribe, prostitution etc. and this will help learners in practising the mentality to fight for them in order to improve the pace of development of the society.

Education helps under-privileged groups and below poverty line families by generating alertness of their plights which provides a boost to them to improve their circumstances. It also assist in recognizing additional points in our communal composition, social gaps and in attaining required acquaintance and skills which are basic fundamentals for accomplishing outstanding growth in the society.

7. Evaluation of Social Change

Education can evaluate social change in society in the form of grinding the intelligence and ascertaining certain principles, values and morals which play important decisive factor for analysis of social change. Through the exploration of significant study, objectionable elements of social change are criticized and discarded and enviable elements of social changes are acknowledged and transmitted.

8. Leadership Role in Social Change

Education can help learners to imbibe leadership responsibility in enhancing competence to confront various types of social tribulations and problem contaminating our society. Learners should be trained leadership roles as social reformers and nation builders and this can be done only with help of education.

9. Economic Development:

Social order is very much required in society for fair play of liberty, parity, social justice and equal chance. Social order can be emerged only with help of education. Economic development is necessary for victuals of new social order and edification act essential role in the economic development of the country by infusing knowledge and skill in the mentality of learners for the enhancement of financial system—the basic fundamental for the country's progress and richness.

Education also assist in organising resources such as human and non- human for accelerating economic advancement of a nation. Education will always be considered as mechanism of economic growth is education because it construct and build up human resource.

10. National Development:

Education helps in opening new outlook of country's enhancement. The key role for nation enhancement comprises each and every views of country to be augmented to its fullest—political, economic, cultural, scientific, social, and development of human resources.

Knowledge base is required for improving the pace of country's development. This could be achieved only when learners are disengaged from normal learning process to innovative learning process which brings social change in society and in the end it results into overall

development of a nation. Education by its objectives, curriculum, techniques and multifaceted functions can bring a revolutionary change in the society.

Intelligence is the principal instrument of societal change and education assist in evolving liberated and inspired minds which acknowledges and circulate social change in its accurate outlook.

Education endows realistic acquaintance and encourages thoughts for development of intelligence which adds to the advancement and modernisation of the society. Role of the educator cannot be ignored because it is a teacher's responsibility not to train learners in negative way but to train them in such a manner that learners can accelerate the transformation in the society.

Conclusion

A right type of social change in society can only be bought with help of right type of education. The function of education in different society and nations divulge the obtrusive note that effectual of educational system establish the swiftness of social change. Education is one of the most prominent instruments of social change in society in spite of hindrances of slow and limited growth of education. Education cannot be perceived as controlling force to protect cultural legacy and agent of social change but it could be perceived as driving force of social and cultural change which is undertaken for improvement of the community to keep in pace with modern changing society.

Education is the only way through which society can bring enviable transformation and modernize itself. A society can be transformed by education only by offering opportunities and skills so that individual can encourage himself for modification with the promising needs and attitude of the changing society. In every phase of existence, social progress requires proper and cautious development –social, cultural, economic, and political. Education must be developed in a right manner so that it fulfils the needs and ambition of the individual as a whole.

An improper and faulty education can pilot unacceptable social changes. So if society wants to transform in accurate path then fundamental awareness is to be given to educational process because education is originator of social change. Environment and socialization techniques are important aspects adding to academic achievement and character building of students.

Social scientist, social psychoanalyst, politicians, instructor and educational planners are considered as an apparatus of social change. In can be concluded that educationists, teachers, colleges and schools have a incredible accountability in social change.

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